

ISic1277

I.Sicily inscription 1277

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. θή[κη]

2. Ἄρτεμ[---]

3. καὶ τοῦ [---]

4. οὐ αὐτοῦ [---]

5. εὐπλ[---]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491445

EDCS 39101646

PHI 140766

PHI 175598

PHI 329722

PHI 330069

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0452 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 26.1073

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 14.0597

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika 6.* Palermo. At 6

Castelli, Gabriello Lancellotto, Principe di Torremuzza 1784. Siciliae et objacentium insularum veterum inscriptionum nova collectio prolegomenis et notis illustrata, et iterum cum emendationibus, & auctariis evulgata. Palermo. At cl.XVIII no.33

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5572

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1277. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4352279>